

FORMING LIBRARY SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: Development of reading among students - the future of our country is in the hands of young people, it is necessary for young people to grow up to be intelligent people who have a broad worldview and can create new ideas and thoughts. Various reading contests, science olympiads, and intellectual games are held among students. A person who reads books everywhere will have a fluent language, beautiful speech, respect, and good economic results. This article discusses the importance and theoretical foundations of the formation of reading skills in students.

Key words: reading, education, culture, psychology, method, artistic work, journalistic work, scientific-theoretical and methodical guide, cultural heritage.

Introduction.

A person must always get food, this is his biological need. Now we need to satisfy not only our biological needs, but our spiritual needs as well. We get spiritual nourishment from books, sources, or when we interact with people.

Unfortunately, now we are only busy with satisfying our ego (biological) needs. If we pay attention to some people, they wear clothes of such and such a company, eat in such and such a restaurant, drive the best car, but if we engage in a little conversation, we will find out how poor their outlook is. True value should be given in relation to our spiritual world and not according to our dress or profession. As long as we judge only by external appearance, the society will also decline. Because our minds are surrounded by these worldly things, and our distance from books (spiritual world) causes us to lose and become narrow-minded people. We often say that we should take a model from abroad so that we can reach the heights they have reached. Let's discuss these things in more detail. What should we imitate in foreign countries? Dressing up, or hairstyles, parties (in other words, men and women can have sex with each other as much as they want, and women walk half-naked)? Tell me, can these things develop us? How correct is it to imitate these things? We should imitate their science, learning, how to develop these sciences, how to work on oneself.

Our wise people say that books are treasures. Knowledge gained from it is wealth. The outlook of every student who reads the book develops, and the possibilities of understanding material existence expand. It's not for nothing that our wise people said, "If you don't have a good conversation partner, read a book." The book is one of the greatest miracles created by human intelligence.

Higher education institutions and their libraries are responsible for solving the following tasks:

- strengthening students' interaction with books, making them interested in reading books, creating a wide opportunity to use books and other information sources in the educational process;

- to make students interested in fiction, to strengthen their need to read books, to teach them to read independently, to pay special attention to the formation of artistic-aesthetics in students through fiction;

- formation of reading culture among students in a consistent manner;

- getting students used to reading the book independently and mastering it creatively;

- to determine students' skills in communicating with books;

- the use of advanced information technologies in the formation of reading culture among students.

In Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the moral development of young people, their upbringing in the spirit of humanity. In the strategic tasks of developing our country and strengthening its independence proposed by our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, volunteers, who can help the society in solving social tasks, are superior in training a mentally mature, well-rounded generation and competitive personnel, and a sense of national pride. Education of young people is defined as one of the important tasks. In the implementation of these tasks, "we rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries, the rich heritage of our ancestors"¹ and educating the growing young generation in the spirit of universal human values built on the basis of Eastern education is a huge responsibility to the society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Of course, the role of school education is incomparable in solving these tasks. In this regard, the head of our state emphasizes to school teachers the issue of forming a culture of reading among students, which is a national characteristic. The famous writer, scientist and translator Azod Sharafiddinov, who is honored as the owner of spiritual courage, described the seven wonders of the world and said, "the seven wonders are the fiery anthem of the human mind, thinking, heart, and the eternal monument dedicated to the greatness of the human genius. is coming. However, despite this, there is another miracle in the world, whose greatness and sanctity is no less than the total glory and beauty of the seven miracles. This miracle is a book. "Many great people have noted that the book is a miracle, even if it is a miracle, it is the first miracle," he writes. For example, the writer and dramatist C. Sveig said, "Where there is a book, a person does not remain alone with himself, within his scope, he is connected to all the universal achievements of the past and the present, the thoughts and ideas of all mankind. he will be familiar with his feelings", he writes. Writer and philosopher J. Swift said, "Books are the children of the mind," pedagogue and writer Ya. Comensky said, "Books are a tool for spreading wisdom," and philosopher and historian F. Bacon said, "Books float in the waves of time and pass their precious burden from generation to generation." - are ships of thought that are passed down to generations," he writes. In this way, great scholars, sages, writers and scientists likened the book to a miracle, a light, a pillar of thinking, a symbol of eternity and spirituality, a source of knowledge, a faithful friend, a mirror of time. Most importantly, the book is an invincible force in the fight against ignorance with enlightenment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

¹ PF-5847-son 08. 10. 2019. O'zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4545884#-4547594>

Aborot resource centers and libraries of educational institutions should become a center for students to communicate and receive information. The library staff working in such libraries should be librarians who can communicate well with students, understand fiction, and have high artistic and aesthetic taste. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the informatization of libraries.

Electronic classrooms and media rooms are being opened. Such special rooms are equipped with specialized equipment for full use of audiovisual materials. A librarian working with students should be ready for librarianship, methodical, research and management activities in his specialty. A librarian should also have such qualities as humanity, love for children, pedagogical thinking.

Promoting the culture of reading among students will prevent many harmful diseases. I.S. Zbarsky emphasized that there are three important components of the formation of reading culture in a person²:

1) Cognitive component - is characterized by the formation of students' spiritual consciousness, artistic erudition, worldview.

2) Emotional component - determined by the formation of aesthetic feelings, emotional value system, higher feelings in students.

Behavioral component - the ability of students to observe social norms of behavior, moral outlook is trained.

Figure 1. Components of formation of reading culture according to I.S. Zbarsky.³

In general, book reading affects the comprehensive development of a person. Ye.P.Suvorov, M.P.Voyushina, Ye.A.Kupirova justified the fact that reading affects the development of a person depending on the direction of activity. In particular, reading accelerates the student's constructive, educational, valuable, communicative, analytical activity. If we take the story of "Sinchalak" alone, Saida Alieva, "even though she is small and humble, she has the energy and enthusiasm to lift the sky" and Arslonbek, who "loses the tip of his sword if a woman leads him." Kalandarov, the images of Eshon, who "can raise a storm from the cough of a flea when it comes to speech" serve as an internal motive for students to build interpersonal relations on a constructive basis, to form a rational altruistic position based on the analysis of moral principles and national values in the relations between society and the individual. . The plots reflecting the interactions and relationships of the characters presented in the works of art activate the student's artistic perception, activate the student's observational ability, empathy, creative imagination, emotional image memory and fluent speech, and lead to the emergence of internal altruistic views of the individual.

² Zbarskiy I.S. Vnekalassnaya rabota po literature(4-8): posobie dlya uchitelya. - M.: Prosveshenie, 2010. – 206 p.

³ Zbarskiy I.S. Vnekalassnaya rabota po literature(4-8): posobie dlya uchitelya. - M.: Prosveshenie, 2010. – 208 p.

Studies aimed at studying the motives of altruism have been conducted in three directions within the framework of all scientific fields. These are:

- a) a learning direction based on D. Wright's views as a criterion of moral behavior;
- b) a research direction based on the research of L. Kohlberg and T. Laikon as the highest example of personal development;
- c) Research in the direction of perfect human characteristics based on the ideas of Eastern scientists and philosophers.

Let's take the story "The Last Victim of War" by our favorite writer O'tkir Hashimov. The story forms students' imaginations that the war took place not only on the front lines, but also in every village, in every household, and the victims of the war were found in every family[6]. In addition, it is stated that even though the hero of the work, Shoikrom, did not go to war, he had to suffer his horror and bitterness at home. The only cow used by the family was stolen, the brother is seriously ill and bedridden, and as if this was not enough, the last food of the children - a handful of strawberries at the edge of the yard - was stolen. Inadequacy and selfish character forces Shoikrom to make a shaky decision. Shoikrom's selfishness creates a sad situation. Through the tragic fate of the hero of the work, it is promoted that the students live surrounded by their own problems and do not receive information about the condition of their loved ones and do not help them. Through the plot of events in the story, Adib encourages students to avoid arrogance, be altruistic, and be devoted to their loved ones.

In order to form the reading culture of students, the librarian needs to be well versed in pedagogy and psychology, to determine the psychology of reading in students, and also to have knowledge of the psychology of interpersonal communication and social psychology. It is necessary for a box store teacher-pedagogue to be aesthetically educated, knowledgeable, and have artistic taste. In developed countries, provision of social, pedagogical and cultural library services to students is part of the sphere of meeting their basic life needs. The main attention of the teacher and librarian should be aimed at forming the reading culture of the student who is developing as a creative person. The rooms intended for the library should be convenient for the student to get information from various sources.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In general, if we conclude on the basis of the above points:

- Reading culture among students serves to increase their spiritual outlook and moral consciousness;
- We can observe the manifestation of altruistic motives based on the science of futuvat in the works of Eastern scholars and legends;
- Altruism is one of the national characteristics based on providing selfless help to others;
- It is possible to form altruistic behavior motives in students by promoting the reading of works of art in coaching hours in schools.

Development of reading among students - the future of our country is in the hands of young people, it is necessary for young people to grow up to be intelligent people with a broad worldview, who can create new ideas and thoughts. Various reading contests, science olympiads, and intellectual games are held among students. A person who reads books everywhere will have a fluent language, beautiful speech, respect, and good economic results. In order to enrich their free time in libraries and their spiritual world, we need to increase their interest in books and prepare them as mature experts in their professions who will be

useful to us in the future. They should be an example to the youth of the future generation, and teach their knowledge in a way that is understandable to the youth of this generation. A person who reads books knows how to ask questions, is not shy in front of others, and has a well-developed worldview.

References:

- 1.PF-5847-No. 08. 10. 2019. On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4545884#-4547594>
- 2.Mirziyoev Sh. M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. - T. : Uzbekistan, 2017. – 488 p.
- 3.Zbarskiy I.S. Vnekalassnaya rabota po literature(4-8): posobie dlya uchitelya. - M.: Prosveshenie, 2010. – 208 s.